

ISMFLUX_data_analysis_pipeline

July 2, 2024

1 ISM-FLUX data analysis pipeline

1.1 Importing libraries and functions

```
[1]: import scipy
import tifffile as tiff
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

from functions import *
```

1.2 Loading MDF and Data

```
[2]: simMDF = tiff.imread(r'simulated_doughnutPSF_2p5nm.tiff')

data = tiff.imread("DNAPaint_Data.tiff")
```

1.3 Choose hot pixels and good channels

```
[3]: listOfHotPixels = [3, 5]
listOfGoodChannels = [i for i in range(25) if i not in listOfHotPixels]
```

```
[4]: Npos = 32 # number of positions
angle = 2 * np.pi / 32 # angle between positions
radiuspx = 15.955312557702428 # radius in pixels (L)
startAngle = 2.3497624612658967 # start angle of the circular scan
```

1.4 Create PSF for all positions

```
[5]: it = 0
PSF11All = np.zeros((32 * 23, 534, 534))

for pos in tqdm(range(32)):
    posAngle = startAngle - (pos * 2 * np.pi / 32) + np.pi
    shiftx = radiuspx * np.cos(posAngle)
    shifty = radiuspx * np.sin(posAngle)
    for c in listOfGoodChannels:
        PSF11All[it, :, :] = np.float32(shift2Darray(simMDF[880-267:880+267,
↪900-267:900+267, c], [shifty, shiftx], None))
```

```

        it += 1

PSF11A11 /= np.max(PSF11A11)
PSF11A11 *= 1023
PSF11A11 = np.clip(PSF11A11, 1, None)

print(np.shape(PSF11A11))

```

100%| | 32/32 [00:03<00:00, 8.20it/s]

(736, 534, 534)

1.5 Data reading and reshaping for analysis

```

[6]: data = np.concatenate(data, 0)

binsize = 1
dataSumCh = np.sum(data[:, :, listOfGoodChannels], 2)
dataTT = np.sum(dataSumCh, 1)
dataBinned = np.add.reduceat(dataTT, np.arange(0, dataTT.size, binsize))
dataTT = dataBinned

plt.figure()
plt.plot(dataTT)

plt.xlabel('Orbit Number')
plt.ylabel('Photon counts per orbit')

```

[6]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Photon counts per orbit')


```
[7]: plt.figure()
hist3 = plt.hist(dataTT, bins=50, color='cyan', edgecolor='k')
plt.xlabel('Photon counts per orbit')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')
```

```
[7]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Frequency')
```


1.6 Fit histogram with 2 Gaussians

```
[8]: fmin = scipy.optimize.least_squares(fit_n_gaussians, x0=(60,20,10,10,70,20),
↳args=(0.5*(hist3[1][0:-1]+hist3[1][1:]), hist3[0]))

x0 = fmin.x
y = hist3[0]
x = hist3[1][0:-1]
xfit = np.linspace(0, x[-1], 300)

A1 = 1e3*x0[0]
x01 = x0[1]
sigma1 = x0[2]

A2 = 1e3*x0[3]
x02 = x0[4]
sigma2 = x0[5]
```

```

g1 = A1 * np.exp(-(xfit-x01)**2 / sigma1**2)
g2 = A2 * np.exp(-(xfit-x02)**2 / sigma2**2)
g3 = 0
g = g1 + g2 + g3

```

```

[9]: findx = np.where(g1 > g2)[0][-1] # find the intersection of the two Gaussians

plt.figure()
plt.hist(dataTT, bins=50, color='cyan', label='Binned data', edgecolor='k')
plt.plot(xfit, g1, ':', c='k')
plt.plot(xfit, g2, ':', c='k')
plt.plot(xfit, g2+g1, 'k')
plt.scatter(0.5*(xfit[findx]+xfit[findx+1]), 0.5*(g1[findx]+g1[findx+1]), s=25,
           c='grey', zorder=4, edgecolor='k')
plt.xlabel('Photon counts per orbit')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')
plt.xlim([0,150])
plt.show()

```


1.7 Plotting example of ON-OFF event in time trace

```

[10]: dt = 32 * 1.92e-3 / 32
time = np.linspace(0, len(dataTT)*dt, int(len(dataTT)))
plt.figure()
plt.plot(1000*(time-470.4), dataTT, 'k')
plt.plot([0, 1000], [x01, x01], ':', color='grey')

```

```
plt.xlim([0, 1000])
plt.ylim([0, 130])
plt.xlabel('Time (ms)')
plt.ylabel('Photon counts per orbit')
# plt.savefig('20231125_06_time_trace.svg')
```

[10]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Photon counts per orbit')

1.8 Choose filter properties for ON-OFF events

```
[11]: photonmin = 13.5
      photonmax = 200
      bgmax = 8
```

1.9 Calculating start and stop of an event

```
[12]: start_stop_indices, start_stop_indices_bg = extract_start_stop_index(dataBinned,
↳ dataTT, photonmin, photonmax, bgmax)
```

```
100%|          | 300000/300000 [00:01<00:00, 250619.27it/s]
100%|          | 300000/300000 [00:00<00:00, 2222265.55it/s]
100%|          | 300000/300000 [00:00<00:00, 3061468.73it/s]
100%|          | 175887/175887 [00:00<00:00, 968939.69it/s]
100%|          | 46925/46925 [00:01<00:00, 45578.55it/s]
100%|          | 22172/22172 [00:00<00:00, 1056053.92it/s]
```

```

[13]: plt.figure()
h1 = plt.hist(start_stop_indices[:, 2], int(np.max(start_stop_indices[:, 2]) +
→1))
dummy = plt.title('Event duration')
plt.ylim([1, 100000])
plt.xlim([0,80])
plt.yscale('log')
plt.xlabel('Time (ms)')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')

plt.figure()
h1 = plt.hist(start_stop_indices[:, 3], 500)
dummy = plt.title('Photons per event')
plt.xlim([0, 5000])
plt.ylim([1, 10000])
plt.yscale('log')
plt.xlabel('Photons')
plt.ylabel('Frequency of events')

plt.figure()
h1 = plt.hist(start_stop_indices[start_stop_indices[:, 2] > 1, 5] / np.
→sqrt(start_stop_indices[start_stop_indices[:, 2] > 1, 4]), 100)
dummy = plt.title('Experimental standard deviation / Poisson noise')
plt.xlabel('Standard deviation / Poisson noise')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')

```

```

[13]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Frequency')

```


1.10 Choose filter properties for valid events

```
[14]: minduration = 5
      maxduration = 500
      minPhotonsEvent = 2000
      maxPhotonsEvent = 10000
      stddevmin = 0
      stddevmax = 2.5
```

```
[15]: # start - stop - duration - photons - average photons - std dev
      valid_events = []
      for i in range(len(start_stop_indices)):
          if minduration <= start_stop_indices[i, 2] <= maxduration and
          ↪minPhotonsEvent <= start_stop_indices[
              i, 3] <= maxPhotonsEvent and stddevmin * np.sqrt(start_stop_indices[i,
          ↪4]) <= start_stop_indices[
              i, 5] <= stddevmax * np.sqrt(start_stop_indices[i, 4]):
              valid_events.append(start_stop_indices[i, :])
      valid_events = np.asarray(valid_events)
      Nevents = len(valid_events)
      print(Nevents)
```

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1.11 Splitting events into 3 chunks

```
[16]: # start - stop - duration - photons - average photons - std dev
      valid_events_chunks = []
      for i in range(len(valid_events)):
          event = valid_events[i]
          chunk_duration = int(np.floor(event[2]/3))
          for j in range(3):
              valid_events_chunks.append([event[0]+j*chunk_duration,
          ↪event[0]+(j+1)*chunk_duration])
      valid_events_chunks = np.asarray(valid_events_chunks)
      Nevents = len(valid_events_chunks)
      print(Nevents)
```

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1.12 Putting photons into an array for parallel processing

```
[17]: n = np.empty((736, Nevents))
      for t in tqdm(range(Nevents)):
          event = valid_events_chunks[t, :]
          dataEvent = np.sum(data[int(event[0]):int(event[1]), :, :], 0) # bin event
          ↪in time (t, alpha, c) -> (alpha, c)
          aa = []
```

```

for pos in range(32):
    for c in listOfGoodChannels:
        aa.append(dataEvent[pos, c])

n[:, t] = aa

```

100%| | 852/852 [00:00<00:00, 3610.29it/s]

1.13 Calculating Maximum Likelihood Estimation

```

[18]: likelihood = LocLikelihoodPyTorch()
lmaps, likelihood_data_scan = likelihood(PSF=PSF11A11[:,50:450,50:450], n=n,
↳SBR0=3.13, SBRvar=False)

```

Constants calculated - GPU Memory usage: 450.61328125 MB

No need to reinitialize the class for the next calculation, Unless PSF is changed

Calculating 852 likelihood maps in 2D mode

Done

1.14 Filtering out events with high standard deviation

```

[19]: # filter output localizations - new filter
threshold = 3.3 # pixels = 10 nm
locs_analysis = []
resolution = []
n_photons = []
for i in range(int(Nevents/3)):
    events = likelihood_data_scan[3*i:3*(i+1),:]
    x = events[:,0]
    y = events[:,1]
    ph = events[:,2]
    xstd = np.std(x)
    ystd = np.std(y)
    resolution.append(2.5*np.sqrt((xstd**2+ystd**2)/2))
    n_photons.append(np.sum(ph))
    #if xstd < threshold and ystd < threshold:
    locs_analysis.append([np.mean(x), np.mean(y), np.sum(ph), np.
↳sqrt((xstd**2+ystd**2)/2), i])

locs_analysis = np.asarray(locs_analysis)
locs_filtered = locs_analysis[locs_analysis[:,3] < threshold]

Nevents_filt = len(locs_filtered)

print(Nevents_filt)

```

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```
[20]: resolution = np.asarray(resolution)
np.median(resolution[resolution<20])
```

[20]: 4.930066485916346

```
[21]: plt.figure()
hist_loc_unc = plt.hist(resolution, 500)
plt.close()
y = hist_loc_unc[0]
y /= np.sum(y)
x = 0.5 * (hist_loc_unc[1][0:-1] + hist_loc_unc[1][1:])
plt.figure()
for i in range(len(x)):
    plt.bar(x[i], y[i], align='center', width=x[2]-x[1], color="cyan",
    ↪edgecolor='k')

plt.plot([np.median(resolution[resolution<20]), np.
    ↪median(resolution[resolution<20])], [0, 35], ':', color='k')
plt.plot([2.5*threshold, 2.5*threshold], [0, 40], color='k')

plt.xlabel('Localization uncertainty (nm)')
plt.ylabel('Frequency')
plt.xlim([0,20])
plt.ylim([0,0.14])
```

[21]: (0.0, 0.14)

1.15 Plotting localizations

```
[22]: im = loc2image(locs_filtered[:, 1], locs_filtered[:, 0], NxOrig=400, upscaling=2.  
↳5, sigma=2, plotFig=False)  
#upscaling = 2.5 to get 1 px = 1 nm because the MDF is simulated at 2.5 nm per  
↳pixel
```

```
[23]: plt.figure()  
plt.imshow(im, cmap='inferno', vmax=0.05)  
plt.xlim([400,800])  
plt.ylim([100,500])  
plt.colorbar()  
plt.gca().set_aspect('equal', adjustable='box')  
  
plt.xlabel('nanometers')  
plt.ylabel('nanometers')
```

```
[23]: Text(0, 0.5, 'nanometers')
```



```
[24]: loc_for_clustering = []  
for i in range(len(locs_filtered)):  
    if locs_filtered[i, 0] < 180 and locs_filtered[i, 1] < 320:  
        loc_for_clustering.append(locs_filtered[i,:])  
loc_for_clustering = np.asarray(loc_for_clustering)
```

```

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=9, random_state=0, n_init="auto").
↳fit(loc_for_clustering[:,0:2])
plt.figure()
plt.scatter(locs_filtered[:, 0], locs_filtered[:, 1], c='grey', edgecolor='k',
↳s=15)
plt.imshow(np.sum(PSF11A11[0::1,50:450,50:450], 0), cmap='inferno')
plt.gca().set_aspect('equal', adjustable='box')
plt.xticks([])
plt.yticks([])

plt.xlim([60,350])
plt.ylim([85,375])

cx = 215
cy = 235
phi = np.linspace(0, 2*3.14, 32)
plt.plot(radiuspx*2/2.5*np.cos(phi)+cx, radiuspx*2/2.5*np.sin(phi)+cy, 'o',
↳c='white')

```

[24]: [[matplotlib.lines.Line2D at 0x27b92b3e470](#)]


```
[25]: loc_for_clustering = []
for i in range(len(locs_filtered)):
    if locs_filtered[i, 0] < 180 and locs_filtered[i, 1] < 350:
        loc_for_clustering.append(locs_filtered[i,:])
loc_for_clustering = np.asarray(loc_for_clustering)

# Multiplying by 2.5 to get 1px = 1 nm
loc_for_clustering[:,0] *= 2.5
loc_for_clustering[:,1] *= 2.5

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=9, random_state=0, n_init="auto").
    ↳fit(loc_for_clustering[:,0:2])
plt.figure()
for i in range(9):
    plt.scatter(loc_for_clustering[kmeans.labels_==i,1],
    ↳loc_for_clustering[kmeans.labels_==i,0], edgecolor='k')
plt.gca().set_aspect('equal', adjustable='box')
plt.title("Localization scatter plot")

plt.xlabel('nanometers')
plt.ylabel('nanometers')

plt.ylim([200, 500])
plt.xlim([450, 750])
```

[25]: (450.0, 750.0)

